

A. Artifact Appendix

A.1 Abstract

To run the VRF’s artifact, the reviewer needs a machine with an Ubuntu and CUDA-enabled GPU. During the evaluation, the reviewer will be required to pull and run Docker images; therefore, Docker and NVIDIA Container Toolkit need to be installed. This artifact supports our paper by demonstrating how to reproduce the reported accuracy results for various datasets.

A.2 Artifact check-list (meta-information)

- **Compilation:** Included in the docker image.
- **Data set:** Download from Google Drive (approximately 22GB).
- **Run-time environment:** Docker container.
- **Hardware:** CUDA-enabled GPU.
- **Metrics:** Accuracy (RTE (cm) & RRE(degree)).
- **Output:** Console output.
- **Experiments:** One experiment for each dataset inside a docker container.
- **How much disk space is required (approximately)?:** 2GB.
- **How much time is needed to prepare workflow (approximately)?:** 1 hour.
- **How much time is needed to complete experiments (approximately)?:** 1 hour.
- **Publicly available?:** Yes.

A.3 Description

A.3.1 How to access

The public GitHub repository contains code artifacts. The link to download the dataset is also included in the repository <https://github.com/nsslofficial/VRF>

A.3.2 Hardware dependencies

The reviewer will need a computer with a CUDA-enabled GPU.

A.3.3 Software dependencies

- Docker
<https://docs.docker.com/engine/install/ubuntu/>
- Nvidia-container-toolkit
<https://docs.nvidia.com/datacenter/cloud-native/container-toolkit/latest/install-guide.html>

A.3.4 Data sets

The dataset needs to run the artifact can be downloaded from Google Drive <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1fstbvPEIsZocvqDT081GufHS9PY8pwoH?usp=sharing>. The dataset consists of 26 sub-datasets which are grouped into 3 main datasets.

- **Carla** (15 datasets)
 - Dataset_1 (5 datasets, D1 to D5)
 - Dataset_2 (5 datasets, D1 to D5)
 - Dataset_3 (5 datasets, D1 to D5)
- **usc_data_accuracy** (5 datasets, D1 to D5)
- **rit_data_accuracy** (6 datasets, D1 to D6)

A.4 Installation

Environmental Setup: Please follow the setup instructions in the provided GitHub repository. The major steps are as follows:

- Install Docker and Nvidia-container-toolkit.
- Pull the docker image.

Build Instructions: Please follow the build instructions in the provided GitHub repository. The major steps are as follows:

- Run the Docker image using the provided bash file. Ensure to make necessary changes to the path of mounted folders according to your system configuration.
- Utilize the Robot Operating Systems (ROS) build tool (catkin make) to compile the code.

A.5 Experiment workflow

To run the experiments follow the run instructions in the provided GitHub repository. The major steps are as follows:

- Download the dataset and place it in the dataset folder mounted with docker.
- Modify the 'setup_env.bash' file according to the dataset for which you want to run the artifact.
- Open five terminals inside the docker and start ros master.
- Source 'setup_env.bash' file in all the terminals.
- Run the instruction in all the five terminals as detailed in the repository.

A.6 Evaluation and expected results

This artifact reproduces the results of Table 3 and Table 9 from the original paper. Running the artifact will generate and save log files in the corresponding dataset folder. Python scripts are utilized to parse and compute the results. Upon completing the experiments, execute the Python scripts inside the Docker to obtain the following results:

- python3 carla_results.py

```
root@ali:/workspace# python3 usc_results.py
----- Table 3 Off-Campus accuracy -----
(420, 3)
RTE(cm) | RRE(degree)
mean    p95    p99    | mean    p95    p99
6.92    16.09  21.70  | 0.42    0.80    1.49
root@ali:/workspace# python3 carla_results.py
----- Table 3 Carla accuracy -----
RTE(cm) | RRE(degree)
mean    p95    p99    | mean    p95    p99
1.55    5.06   6.59   | 0.05    0.11    0.15
----- Table 9 results -----
Traffic | Alignment Error
        | RTE(cm)  RRE(degree)
Low     | 1.43     0.04
Medium  | 1.65     0.04
High    | 1.59     0.04
root@ali:/workspace#
```

- python3 usc_results.py

```
----- Table 3 Off-Campus accuracy -----
(420, 3)
RTE(cm) | RRE(degree)
mean    p95    p99    | mean    p95    p99
6.92    16.09  21.70  | 0.42    0.80    1.49
root@ali:/workspace#
```

- python3 rit_results.py

```
root@ali:/workspace# python3 rit_results.py
----- Table 3 On-Campus accuracy -----
-----
RTE(cm) | RRE(degree)
mean    p95    p99    | mean    p95    p99
4.96    15.78  22.36  | 0.08    0.21   0.39
root@ali:/workspace#
```

A.7 Experiment customization

Before running the artifact for each dataset, it's necessary to modify the 'setup env.bash' file. Specific modifications for each dataset are listed in the 'Setup Environment' section of the GitHub repository. Please refer to this section for detailed instructions on how to locate and modify the 'setup env.bash' file accordingly.

A.8 Notes

Carla dataset: The Carla dataset consists of three sub-datasets: Dataset_1, Dataset_2, and Dataset_3. Each of these sub-datasets comprises five different datasets (D1 to D5). The results of these smaller datasets (D1 to D5) are concatenated into one file. It is necessary to run the code for these datasets in order (starting with D1, followed by D2, and so on to D5) because the ground truth for these datasets is also concatenated in the same order